

////////////////////////////////////

THE USABILITY OF AUGMENTED REALITY SUPPORTING THE MOCKUP MAKING IN INDUSTRIAL DESIGN LEARNING.

Chun-Di Chen / Chang-Hung Tsai / Chun-Ching Chen*
National Taipei University of Education / National Taipei University of Technology*
cdcvic@tea.ntue.edu.tw / Keanu.k@gmail.com / cceugene@ntut.edu.tw

ABSTRACT

Given that fact that the physical and virtual models are seldom inter-referred for the development of 3D form in design in current design learning, this paper proposed that the AR system could potentially improve the inter-reference. This study explores the usability of AR system and conducts a design trail where 30 participants recruited and take a mockup-making work with the assistance from the AR system. Each participant was asked to make three mockups with different levels of complexity; simple, moderate, and complex. Questionnaire and interview survey is given to the participant in order to collect the data for the analysis. The analysis includes three aspects, the frequency of marker adjustment, the subjective survey to the satisfaction, and the workload. Results indicate that the AR system does provide useful visual information to reduce the uncertainty in form, particularly to the complex form, and to facilitate the mockup making.

Keywords: augmented reality, industrial design, usability.

INTRODUCTION

Industrial design can be understood from various perspectives (Lucie-Smith, 1983; Heskett, 1980). McDermott (1992) simply considered that industrial design is a term covering the mass-manufacturing products of the post-industrial revolution society. The need of team work in design to achieve the success has been discussed broadly (Baxter, 1995; Wright, 1998; Walsh, 1992) in which the need for group effort results in considerable communication and knowledge sharing between design team members, and various kinds of visual information are

employed to present and explicate sources of inspiration, ideas, concepts, and problems.

Broadly speaking, the outcome of designing is the specification of an object that, when made, people will see, touch and interact with. Given the primacy of the visual sense in the apprehension of objects, the corresponding dominance of drawings and three-dimensional models in design specification is not too surprising

Indeed, in the design learning practice, the sketch is often used as an outcome of design development for the checkpoint need in mid-term, while the physical mockup is mainly applied for the presentation, making little inter-reference during the concept development. Such a dilemma might reduce the effectiveness and efficient of the students' learning in 3D form design.

Moreover, given the value of physical mockup comparing to virtual 3D model in visual and tactile communication (Lee & Park, 2005), an incorrect physical model will influence the evaluation to the concept in the design discussion, even the learning in the form design.

According, given the affordance of augmented reality in mixing the images in the real and virtual worlds, many research have addressed the benefits using augmented reality in product design. However, the usability is seldom focused, leaving a gap to applying the AR system as a tool to support the team work in form study. Therefore, this article studied the usability of augmented reality in supporting the design students to make mockup, with a view to

reinforce the cooperative or personal works in concept development and form study.

CONCEPT DEVELOPMENT AND DIGITAL TOOLS

The increasing development in CAID has changed the process in developing the form of 3D concept, making the physical mockup less used in supporting the concept development. Alternative, the students present the 3D appearance of the developing concept using digital tools after the hand drawing draft in the early stage. As the result, the 3D form would be difficult to be carefully considered and the learning in 3D form would be unsatisfied to the purpose of teaching-learning.

On the other hand, the recent development in digital technology has reduced the distance between the physical and virtual world. For example, the RP technology allows the 3D digital form to be visual realized in physical form during a short duration. Also, the augmented reality (AR) provides the environment to present the images of physical and virtual models in the same screen. Many research an experimental work have explored the opportunity using AR system to support the design work. Lee and Park (2005) argues the importance of interaction in tactile sensation, since neither 2D nor 3D image of the development product could provide the full-scale feeling and recognition, leading AR system being a potential tools in supporting 3D design work. Klinker, et al., (2002) used mobile AR application to study the relation of developing car and the show room to refine the appearance of car as well as the style of collaborative design work. Verlinden and Horvath (2007) proposed a called IAP (Interactive Augmented Prototyping) system which combines the AR and RP features, to improve the express of materials and surface, and innovation and design outcomes.

Figure 1 illustrates the key features of AR system enabling the user to interact with physical and virtual image in the same place at the same time. Given the above, this study proposes that the augmented reality (AR) could facilitate the designers to make a smoothly inter-reference between the physical and virtual models, driving a progress to the mockup making. Here it is assumed that the more complexity of the form is, the more difficult for the

Figure 1. Features of AR system

mockup making is. Hence, the main issue in this study is to study the influence of different complexity to the mockup making work in the AR system.

Three assumptions were proposed in this study as following:

1. The numbers of marker adjustment could be significantly influenced by the complexity of the form.
2. The users' satisfaction of mockup-making work could be significantly influenced by the complexity of the form.
3. The workloads of mockup-making work could be significantly influenced by the complexity of the form.

TRIAL DESIGN

In order to study the usability of AR system in supporting the mockup-making in the concept development stage of industrial design project, a design trial is arranged where the participants were asked to take mockup-making works by referring to the image of the virtual model in the AR system. The virtual model represents a product (water bottle) and was drawn, pre-installed in and calibrated for the AR system that is a high-end PC with a 22 " LCD monitor, and mounted with a webcam. Simulating the general desktop of design studio, the distance between the participant and the monitor is about 80cm, enabling the participant the to see the images of physical and virtual model in the AR screen at the same time.

Thirty design students having at least one year experience in mockup making were recruited. Each participant has to complete three mockups with different levels of complexity in form (A, B, C, from

simple, moderate and complex respective). A 30 minutes brief session was given to each participant to understand the coming design work in this trial and familiarize the AR system. In the formal design trial, 30 participants were equally grouped into A and B. Each participant in Group A took the model-making work with the order from simple to complex, and then to moderate, whilst for Group B, the order is from the moderate to complex, then to simple.

Figure 2. The mockup with 3 different levels of complexity (simple to complex, from left to right).

Each session recruited one participant who and the researcher located at an isolated and quiet room simulated to a design studio in which a cubic PU (20cm x 20cm x 20cm, pens and paper, a set of hand-craft tools for model making are placed on a studio table accompanying with a PC with AR system.

Considering the cost, and the limits of practical design work environment, the trial does not use markerless AR system although such a system might provide more convenient means of discussion and operation for the users. The used AR system in the design trial composed of a 22" monitor, a high resolution webcam and a high-end PC, which could easily be applied in ordinary design office. The 22" monitor allows the images of mockup to be full-scale represented in the screen, making a comparable image in size to the physical mockup in hand.

The trial work started at a number of pilot studies to test the stability of AR system, the layout of workspace, and the need to adjust the difference of complexity in the referred three images of product. Results suggest needing to provide the images of virtual model from the 3 isometric points of view, the system optimum to improve the stability of the AR system and the overall duration in each session.

In the formal trial session, the researcher checked the AR system and the afforded tools for mockup-making prior to the entrance of the participants. During the formal trial session, the researcher did not join the model making work, but take care to maintain the AR system workable and the recording devices for the following analysis work. However, in the case the participants looked for help due to the breakdown of AR system, the research would give her/him the needed assistance.

During each session, a 15-minute span is given to the mockup-making work, and followed by a questionnaire survey for about 10 minutes. Totally, three mockup making works and three questionnaire survey were conducted in the formal trial. Finally, a 10-minutes interview was conducted to obtain the participants' opinion about the usage. Overall duration for a formal trial lasts about 90 minutes. Figure 3 shows the process of the trial.

THE ANALYSIS

Many methods for usability evaluation were discussed on literature. Earlier, Nielsen (1993) suggested five criteria including learnability, efficiency, memorability, error rate, and satisfaction. Stanton (1998), according to ISO 9241, discussed thee key criteria for the usability evaluation: effectiveness,

Figure 3. The process and duration of each mockup-making, questionnaire and interview survey in the formal trial.

efficiency, and satisfaction. Frøkjær et al., (2000) also have the similar suggestions.

Wixon & Wilson (1997) emphasize the importance of subjective feeling in the evaluation. In fact, many researchers have suggested different method for the evaluation by means of the particular context. For example, Shneiderman(1998) discussed the relation between learnability and memorability, and suggested a need for a more detailed identification to these criteria, while Shackel (1991) and Preece (1994) argued the value of flexibility in usage, and suggested flexibility playing determinedly in subjective satisfaction .

Give these methods for usability evaluation addressed on literature, this study adopts three kinds of data for the analysis of the usability of the given AR system. The three aspects were the adjusting frequency of AR marker during the modeling process, the measurement of workload, and the subjective satisfaction in terms of System Usability Scale (SUS).

During the mockup making process, the participants have two essential activities appeared iteratively; the action on the model, and the adjustment to the marker to change the angle of images appearing in AR system. Since the adjustment is necessary to the completion of the mockup making, the frequency of the marker adjustment could indicate the difficulty to achieve the better inter-reference between the virtual object and the mockup. This aspects concerns with the extent to which the participants have to coordinate the two kinds of images in the AR screen; one from the digital virtual model, and the other one from the mockup captured by video camera.

The second and the third are questionnaire surveys conducted after each 15-minutes model-making. To the participants, the mockup-making work drives them to take care a number of tasks at the same time, say, adjusting the marker and check the angles of the mockup and the virtual model at the same time. In fact, workload is an important factor in evaluating the usability of a complex system in which the subjective evaluation is increasing recommended because of the difficulty in measure the

effectiveness under a multi-task workload (Rubio, et al, 2004). Furthermore, NASA-TLX lists six criteria for the measurement of workload; they are mental demands, physical demands, temporal demands, effort, own performance, and frustration (Hart, & Staveland, 1998). In this study, as the participants have to deal with multiple tasks concurrently, the subjective evaluation would be a useful method to measure the workload in terms of the questionnaire survey arranged with a 7-level Likert scale.

The third method is a 5-level Likert scale comprising 10 questions for the evaluation of subjective satisfaction.

The interview survey addresses two issues; the convenience from the AR system in assisting mock-up making, and the difference in usage of AR system for different level of complexity.

THE RESULTS

The statistical analysis to the frequency of marker adjustment indicates a positive correlation between the complexity of form and the frequency of marker adjustment ($F=394.551$, $p= 0.000 < 0.05$). In other words, the more complex of the model is, the more frequency of the marker adjustment is.

However, the excessive less in the frequency of marker adjustment ($m=0.42$) might imply the less usage of AR system in supporting the making to simple model, since to the simple form, the participants could easily overpass the images of mockup in the screen, and compare the images of the virtual model, and of the mockup in hand.

Meanwhile, the analysis of workload also points out that the complexity of form affects the workload ($F=117.454$, $p= 0.000 < 0.05$) in which all 6 subscales reach the statistical significance, indicating that the complexity of form would increase the workload of mockup making as well as the operation to the AR system.

The results of subjective satisfaction survey suggest that the complexity of form plays determinately in the subject satisfaction to the AR system, particularly to the most complex form in which the

lower satisfaction gains the significant difference in comparing with the other two kinds of forms. It is surprised that the highest satisfaction is gained in the assist to the making of moderate form. In general, AR system was evaluated to be easy learnt and used, and needs not technician's help.

CONCLUSION

Briefly, this study examines the dilemma in using mockup and computer-simulated model in industrial design learning, and argues that AR system is potentially useful to reduce the dilemma by increasing the possibility of inter-reference between the two kinds of model. The analysis result suggests that AR system is helpful in general. However, the too simple form could reduce the need in using AR system while the too complex form will increase the workload and difficulty in adjusting the AR system, making less usability, indicating the further need in technical development.

REFERENCES

- Baxter, M. (1995). Product design, practical methods for the systematic development of new products. London: Chapman & Hall, pp. 19, 235.
- Frøkjær, E., Hertzum, M., & Hornbæk, K. (2000). Measuring usability: Are effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction really correlated? In: Proceedings of CHI 2000 Human Factors in Computing Systems. ACM Press, pp. 345-352
- Hart, S. G. & Staveland, L. E. (1988). Development of NASA-TLX (Task Load Index): Results of empirical and theoretical research. In: P. A. Hancock and N. Meshkati (Eds.) Human Mental Workload. Amsterdam: North Holland Press.
- Heskett, J. (1980). Industrial design. Reprinted, Singapore: Thames and Hudson Ltd, pp. 7-9
- Klinker, G., Dutoit, A.H., Bauer, M., Bayer, J., Novak, V., & Matzke, D., (2002). Fata morgana – A presentation system for product design. ISMAR'02, pp.76.
- Lee, W., & Park, J. (2005). Augmented foam: A tangible augmented reality for product design, ISMAR'05, pp. 5-8, 106-109.
- Lucie-Smith, D. (1983). A history of industrial design. Great Britain: Phaidon Press Limited, pp. 117
- McDermott, C. (1992). Essential design. London: Bloomsbury Publishing Limited, pp 127
- Nielsen, J. (1993). Usability engineering, San Diego, CA: Academic Press.
- Preece, J. (1994). Human-Computer interaction, NY: Addison-Wesley.
- Rubio, S., Diaz, E., Martin, J., & Puente, J. M. (2004). Evaluation of subjective mental workload: a comparison of SWAT, NASA-TLX and workload profile methods. *Appl. Psychol. Int. Rev.* 53(1), 61-86.
- Sandor, C, & Klinker, G. (2005). A rapid prototyping software infrastructure for user interface in ubiquitous augmented reality. *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing*, 9(3), 169-185.
- Shackel, B. (1991). Usability- Context, framework, definition, design and evaluation. In: B. Shackel and S. Richardson (Eds.), Human Factors for Informatics Usability, Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 21-38.
- Shneiderman, B. (1998). Designing the user interface. 3rd (Ed) Boston, MA: Addison-Wesley Longman, Inc.
- Stanton, N. (1998). Product design with people in mind, In N. Stanton (Eds.) Human Factors in Consumer Products, London: Taylor & Francis, pp. 1-17.
- Verlinden, J., & Horváth, I., (2007). A critical systems position on augmented prototyping system for industrial design. Proceedings of the ASME 2007 International Design Engineering Technical Conferences & Computers and Information in Engineering Conference, IDETC/CIE 2007, Las Vegas, Nevada, USA
- Walsh, V., Roy, R., Bruce, M., and Potter, S. (1992). Winning by design: Technology, product design and international competitiveness. Great Britain: Blackwell Publishers, pp 50-54.
- Wixon, D., & Wilson, C. (1997). The usability engineering framework for product design and evaluation, In: M. Helander, T.K. Landauer, & P.V. Prabhu (Ed) Handbook of Human-Computer Interaction, NY: Elsevier Science, 653-688.
- Wright, I. (1998). Design methods in engineering and product design. Berkshire: McGraw-Hill, pp. 47-52.